

1 **Effectors of wheat and barley powdery mildew pathogens (*Blumeria* spp.): A**
2 **molecular perspective**

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11 **Abstract**

12 To invade and proliferate on the host, pathogens manipulate host physiology through
13 the secretion of virulence factors (effectors). The molecular functions of effectors inside
14 plant hosts, in particular the mechanisms for inhibiting the plants immune system, have
15 been of interest in the field of molecular plant-microbe interactions. Obligate biotrophic
16 pathogens, such as rusts and powdery mildews, cannot proliferate outside of plant
17 hosts. In addition to the inhibition of the plant's immune components, these pathogens
18 are therefore under particular pressure to efficiently extract nutrients from the host.
19 Understanding the molecular basis of infections mediated by obligate biotrophic
20 pathogens is of significance because of their impact in modern agriculture. Due to
21 constraints with regard to the genetic accessibility of obligate biotrophic fungi, the
22 functional analysis of effectors derived from these fungi lags significantly behind those
23 of other fungal phytopathogens. In addition to their relevance in agriculture, powdery
24 mildews serve as excellent model for research on obligate biotrophic cereal
25 pathogens. Here, we summarise the current knowledge on putative molecular
26 virulence functions of protein effectors secreted by the obligate biotrophic grass

27 powdery mildews (*Blumeria* spp.) to modulate disease. This review aims to give an
28 overview on the current knowledge of the barley and wheat powdery mildews
29 effecterome, emphasizing the methodological approaches used for assessing the
30 candidate effectors virulence traits and associated functional studies. We highlight
31 recent progress in the field, identify unresolved questions, and provide a roadmap for
32 future research to advance our understanding of these critical plant pathogens.

33

34 Keywords: *Blumeria*, barley, wheat, effectors, CSEPs, fungi

35

36 **Introduction**

37 Pathogens that have adapted to specific host environments possess the ability to
38 secrete a diverse array of virulence factors, many of which are small, secreted proteins
39 (Dodds and Rathjen 2010). Upon secretion from the fungus, effectors act in the host's
40 apoplast or translocate into the cell interior (Stergiopoulos and De Wit 2009). Several
41 well-characterised fungal effector proteins target various host components to either
42 disrupt the plant's immune system and establish infection or to manipulate the host's
43 metabolic processes to promote pathogen nourishment and proliferation (Lo Presti et
44 al. 2015; Ökmen and Doehlemann 2014).

45 Confronted with these diverse pathogenic effectors, plants have evolved resistance
46 (*R*)-genes with recognition specificities towards some of these effectors. These *R*-
47 genes often encode for cell-surface-localised receptors or intracellular nucleotide-
48 binding leucine-rich repeat receptors (NLRs), both of which recognize specific
49 pathogen effectors, in the apoplast or inside of the cell, respectively. Effectors
50 recognised by immune receptors are commonly referred to as avirulence effectors
51 (AVRs). Upon recognition of AVRs, immune receptors trigger a series of downstream

52 responses that diminish or terminate infection. These responses are frequently
53 accompanied by a cell death reaction of the infected tissue, the hypersensitive
54 response (HR), and are also referred to as effector-triggered immunity (ETI) (Cui et al.
55 2015; Dodds and Rathjen 2010; Saur and Hükelhoven 2021). Based on the
56 evolutionary concept that host immune receptors recognise important pathogen
57 virulence factors, understanding the molecular functions of avirulence effectors has
58 been of particular interest in the field of plant-microbe interactions.

59 **Obligate biotrophic powdery mildew pathogens infect economically important** 60 **cereal crop plants**

61 Obligate biotrophic powdery mildew fungi are ascomycetes that represent some of the
62 most severe plant pathogens globally, infecting a wide range of hosts exceeding 9,000
63 dicot and 650 monocot species (Glawe 2008; Takamatsu 2013). Powdery mildew fungi
64 of the *Blumeria* genus are detrimental and economically severe plant pathogens as
65 they infect key cereal crops essential for food security, including wheat (*Triticum*
66 *aestivum*) and barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) (Dean et al. 2012).

67 The infection process starts with the contact of the fungal conidiospores with the host
68 leaf surface and the formation of the primary germ tube. The spores form a secondary
69 germ tube that evolves into the appressorium, which enters the epidermal cell wall
70 through a so-called penetration peg, that eventually leads to the formation of a
71 specialized fungal feeding structure inside the host cell (Both et al. 2005; Hükelhoven
72 and Panstruga 2011). This specialised organ, known as the haustorium, is separated
73 from the host cell interior by the host-derived extrahaustorial membrane (Hükelhoven
74 and Panstruga 2011; Kwaaitaal et al. 2017) and it is presumed to serve as the primary
75 site for the exchange of molecules between the host and fungal cell (Fig. 1). Effectors
76 are proposed to be partly synthesized in and translocated from the haustoria to the

77 host cell to support successful infection (Bushnell 1972; Mapuranga et al. 2022;
78 Panstruga 2003). To date it is unclear if *Blumeria* effectors translocate from the infected
79 epidermal cells to the underlying mesophyll tissue (Fig. 1). But because the production
80 of carbohydrates occurs in the mesophyll tissue, at least these nutrients must be
81 reallocated from the healthy mesophyll to the infected epidermal cells.

82 The best studied grass powdery mildew fungi are *Blumeria graminis* forma specialis
83 *tritici* (*Bgt*, formerly *Erysiphe graminis* f.sp. *tritici*) and *Blumeria hordei* (*Bh*, formerly
84 known as *Erysiphe graminis* f.sp. *hordei* and *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *hordei*) that exhibit
85 narrow host specificities towards wheat and barley, respectively. Both species serve
86 as excellent model organisms for studying cereal powdery mildew disease and obligate
87 biotrophy in fungi in general (Dean et al. 2012; Liu et al. 2021). Obligate biotrophic
88 pathogens can only survive and proliferate on living host cells and rely on nutrient
89 acquisition from the host plant. In fact, powdery mildew fungi lack the typical
90 ascomycete genes that usually encode for proteins important for carbohydrate
91 degradation, enzymes of the primary or secondary metabolism and transporters
92 (Spanu et al. 2010; Wicker et al. 2013). *Blumeria* fungi primarily reproduce asexually.
93 Individual *Blumeria* strains/isolates differ in their subset of avirulence effectors
94 (Frantzeskakis et al. 2018; Lu et al. 2016) and this variation underlies the varying
95 virulence phenotypes between isolates on different host plant varieties (Dreiseitl 2014),
96 based on the isolate-specific resistance genes present in the respective cultivars
97 (Jorgensen and Wolfe 1994; Maekawa et al. 2019; Seeholzer et al. 2010).

98 ***Blumeria* effectors in the jungle of nomenclature and different genome** 99 **assemblies**

100 The genomic era combined with proteomics approaches allowed the identification of
101 the first candidate effectors in the first *Bh* isolate DH14 genome assembly and these

102 have been named candidates for secreted effector proteins (CSEPs) (Pedersen et al.
103 2012; Spanu et al. 2010) or *B*lumeria effector candidates (BECs) (Bindschedler et al.
104 2009, 2011). Some of these had also been detected independently in the proteome of
105 *Bh* haustoria and were called Effector candidates (Efcs) (Godfrey et al. 2009). The
106 initial list of CSEP genes encompassed 248 members, which are highly expressed
107 genes encoding secreted proteins without transmembrane domains. An additional
108 criterium for a secreted protein to classify as CSEP was the lack of homology to
109 proteins outside of the powdery mildew family (Spanu et al. 2010), based on the
110 observation that fungal effectors frequently lack homologous proteins outside of the
111 taxonomic family of the pathogen under study (Panstruga and Dodds 2009; Tyler et al.
112 2006). By combining genomic, transcriptomic, and proteomic approaches with the
113 previously available datasets, Pedersen et al. 2012 generated an easily accessible list
114 of *Bh* CSEPs, providing a fantastic resource for future functional studies on CSEPs.
115 The list encompassed 491 CSEP members (CSEP0001 – CSEP0492, lacking
116 CSEP0427, presumably due to duplicated annotation) (Spanu, personal
117 communication). Out of the 491 identified CSEP genes, 407 group into 72 families of
118 paralogs, while 84 of them remained as singletons that could not be assigned to any
119 family based on sequence analysis (Pedersen et al. 2012). Seven of these families
120 include 11 or more members, making them some of the most important larger gene
121 families in the *Bh* genome, as only 25 families in the entire predicted *Bh* proteome were
122 found to contain more than ten members in *in silico* analyses (Pedersen et al. 2012;
123 Spanu et al. 2010).

124 More recently, near-chromosome level assemblies of *Bh* isolate DH14 identified 805
125 secretion signal peptide-containing protein-coding genes (SPs) in the DH14 reference
126 genome (Frantzeskakis et al. 2018; GenBank: OENG01000029.1) Importantly, this list
127 contains all putatively secreted protein genes without the application of further criteria

128 (Frantzeskakis et al. 2018; Additional file 1, Table 7). The majority of the previously
129 identified 492 CSEPs are present in this list of 805 SP genes, however, some are
130 missing based on differential criteria for secretion signals applied. Most recently, this
131 list was reassessed *in silico* to re-predict CSEPs (Sabelleck et al. 2024). EffectorP 3.0
132 predictions led to the classification of 527 proteins as effector candidates. Importantly,
133 this most recent effector candidate list includes most of the CSEPs for which a plant
134 target could be identified (see below in section 'Host interactors of *Blumeria* CSEPs')
135 and most known *Bh* AVR_A effectors (Sabelleck et al. 2024). As such, we suggest to
136 make use of this resource for future work on *Bh* CSEPs.

137 In *Bgt*, candidate effector identification has relied only on *in silico* methods. The first
138 reference assembly for the *Bgt* isolate CHE_96224 was published by Wicker et al.
139 2013. In this study, candidate secreted effector proteins (CSEPs) were identified using
140 the following criteria: the presence of a signal peptide and the absence of homology to
141 known proteins. This approach led to the identification of 437 CSEPs, all of which had
142 homologs in *Bh*. The observation that *Bh/Bgt* CSEP homolog pairs exhibited higher
143 ratios non-synonymous substitutions per non-synonymous site (dN) over synonymous
144 substitutions per synonymous site (dS) (dN/dS) compared to non-CSEP genes
145 provided an additional criterion for the identification of potential novel candidate
146 effectors. By applying a dN/dS ratio cutoff of 0.5 for *Bh/Bgt* homologs, 165 genes were
147 selected and designated as candidate effector proteins (CEPs). These CEPs do not
148 contain a signal peptide, leading the authors to hypothesize that they might be secreted
149 *via* non-conventional secretion pathways. Overall, this first version of the candidate
150 effector complements of *Bgt* isolate CHE_96224 included 602 members, comprising
151 both CSEPs and CEPs (Wicker et al. 2013).

152 The CHE_96224 reference genome was reannotated in 2017 using transcriptomic data
153 and led to an updated candidate effectorome for *Bgt* CHE_96224 (Praz et al. 2017).
154 Here the newly predicted *Bgt* proteome was clustered with proteomes from *Bh*,
155 *Podospora anserina*, *Neurospora crassa* into protein families using a markov cluster
156 algorithm. Protein clusters containing only *Bh* and *Bgt* proteins with at least one
157 member with a predicted signal peptide and without a transmembrane domain were
158 classified as candidate effectors. The final effector complement identified by this
159 method consistent of 597 candidate effectors.

160 In 2019, a new reference genome for CHE_96224 was created using PacBio
161 sequencing (Müller et al. 2019), resulting in a genome assembly with all eleven *Bgt*
162 chromosomes resolved (genome assembly *Bgt_genome_v3_16*). To maximize the
163 identification of candidate effectors, including potentially unconventional ones, a
164 genome-wide scan was conducted to identify previously unannotated open reading
165 frames encoding a signal peptide. Following this step, clustering of proteins was
166 performed using the approach described by Praz et al. 2017. Protein clusters with only
167 members from *Bgt/Bh* with more than 10% of their members containing a signal
168 peptide and no homology to transposable elements were classified as candidate
169 effectors. In contrast, clusters with fewer than 10% signal peptide-containing members
170 or with homology to transposable elements were classified as weak effectors. This
171 process resulted in the annotation of 844 candidate effector genes that group into 171
172 candidate effector families and this list of candidate effectors is publicly available on
173 Zenodo (Müller 2024).

174 Notably, unlike in *Bh*, CSEPs and CEPs in *Bgt* were not assigned CSEP identifiers but
175 were referred to by their gene identifiers. These identifiers were retained across
176 different reference assembly versions to avoid confusion.

177 In summary, on the genomic level, grass powdery mildews are well described and the
178 genomic and transcriptomic data on hundreds of different *Blumeria* isolates are
179 available (Hacquard et al. 2013; Kloppe et al. 2023; Kunz et al. 2023; Lu et al. 2016;
180 Menardo et al. 2016, 2017; Müller et al. 2022; Praz et al. 2017, 2018; Saur et al. 2019a;
181 Sotiropoulos et al. 2022; Velásquez-Zapata et al. 2023; Wicker et al. 2013; Zeng et al.
182 2017). For future molecular biology research on the grass powdery mildews, we
183 suggest the use of long-read based genome assemblies for which accession details
184 can be found in Table 1. All gene sequences from *Bgt* reference isolate CHE_96224
185 can be directly accessed at the NCBI nucleotide database, whereas the gene
186 sequences of strains ISR_7 and CHVD_042201 assemblies are only available via
187 Zenodo repositories (Kunz et al. 2022, 2024b). *Bh* gene IDs based on the older short-
188 read genome assembly, including those for CSEP genes (Spanu et al. 2010), may be
189 compared to those provided in the updated DH14 genome assembly by accessing the
190 by Frantzeskakis et al. 2018 provided Additional File 1, Table S3 'Association table for
191 old and new *Bh* isolate DH14 gene model ID', which also highlights differences in gene
192 sequences between gene models from previous and updated genome assemblies.
193 Sabelleck et al. 2024, Supplementary Table 1 provides the most-updated list of CSEP
194 genes and encoded proteins, including respective sequences.

195 ***Blumeria* AVR effectors are predicted candidate effectors**

196 Recent advancement in sequencing technology and improved functional assays for
197 the determination of avirulence effectors have fuelled the identification of AVR effectors
198 in *Bgt* and *Bh*. The *Bh* avirulence effectors AVR_{A1}, AVR_{A6}, AVR_{A7}, AVR_{A9}, AVR_{A10},
199 AVR_{A13} AND AVR_{A22}, that are recognised by the barley NLRs MLA1, MLA6, MLA7,
200 MLA9, MLA10, MLA13 and MLA22, respectively, were identified (Bauer et al. 2021; Lu
201 et al. 2016; Saur et al. 2019a). In parallel, nine *Bgt* AVR effectors have been isolated,

202 namely AVRPM1A_1, AVRPM1A_2, AVRPM2, AVRPM3^{A2/F2}, AVRPM3^{B2/C2},
203 AVRPM3^{D3}, AVRPM8, AVRPM17 and AVRPM60, that are recognised by the wheat
204 NLRs PM1A, PM2, PM3A, PM3F, PM3D, PM3C, PM3D and PM60 and rye NLRs PM8
205 and PM17 respectively (Bourras et al. 2015, 2019; Hewitt et al. 2021; Kloppe et al.
206 2023; Kunz et al. 2023; Müller et al. 2022; Praz et al. 2017). The avirulence function of
207 these effectors, i.e. their ability to activate immune responses and cell death mediated
208 by the matching MLA/PM NLRs provide evidence that the gene products of these AVR
209 genes indeed act as fungal effectors. Although these studies did not involve studies on
210 the intrinsic virulence function of the AVR effectors, the fact that all these AVR_A effectors
211 belong to the list of predicted effector candidates is of significance as it provided
212 genetic proof that CSEPs and CEPs are functional effector proteins. Important to
213 mention is also the fact that the majority of *Bgt AvrPm* had been previously detected
214 among the highest expressed genes in *Bgt*. The same holds true for the majority of *Bh*
215 AVR_a effector genes, that in addition were also detected at the proteome level in MS
216 studies of *Bh* haustoria and infected barley epidermal cells (Bindschedler et al. 2009,
217 2011; Godfrey et al. 2009; Pedersen et al. 2012). The exceptions are AVR_{a9}
218 (*BLGH_04994*, *CSEP0174*) and AVR_{a6} (*BLGH_00709*, a variant of *CSEP0254*)
219 (Ahmed et al. 2016; Bauer et al. 2021; Pedersen et al. 2012). The latter was potentially
220 not identified due to the constraints of short-read-genome assemblies that did not
221 contain a gene model for AVR_{a6}/*BLGH_00709*, again emphasising the benefits of the
222 long-read genome assemblies (Table 1). In summary, this underlines that although not
223 entirely comprehensive, the results from proteomic approaches provide a useful
224 resource for the identification of truly secreted effector proteins from cereal powdery
225 mildews.

226 Importantly, map-based cloning approaches had initially suggested non-CSEP genes
227 to encode AVR_{A10} and AVR_{K1} and these Class I LINE retrotransposons, whose gene

228 products lack signal peptides were suggested to be recognised by MLA10 and MLK1
229 (Ridout et al. 2006). Subsequent availability of the *Blumeria* fungal genomes
230 (Frantzeskakis et al. 2018; Saur et al. 2019a; Spanu et al. 2010) combined with the
231 development of functional assays for the determination of avirulence effectors from
232 obligate biotrophs (Lu et al. 2016; Saur et al. 2019a, 2019b) demonstrated that actually
233 the *csep0141* gene (*BLGR_10013*) encodes AVR_{A10}, based on the fact that this
234 CSEP141 variant (CSEP141 I77F) acts as the genetic determinant for MLA10
235 activation. The previously identified gene was therefore re-named to EKA_AVR_{a10} in
236 this study (Saur et al. 2019a). We suggest to retain this nomenclature for clarity.
237 Notably, EKA_AVR_{a10} or retrotransposons in general might well encode *Bh* virulence
238 factors (Amselem et al. 2015). For example, independent studies demonstrated that
239 the *Bh* SINE-like retroposable element *Eg-R1* encodes the non-CSEP-like ROP-
240 interactive peptide 1 (ROPIP1), which in turn acts as a virulence factor, likely by
241 mediating microtubule network destabilization (McCollum et al. 2020; Nottensteiner et
242 al. 2018).

243 **CSEPs as virulence factors**

244 Although there is evidence that certain CSEPs indeed act as *Blumeria* virulence
245 effectors, the large number of CSEPs paired with the difficulties to genetically modify
246 obligate biotrophs makes it still challenging to experimentally identify the effectors with
247 the most crucial virulence function during host infection. Generally, avirulence effectors
248 and small secreted protein-encoding genes that are conserved and highly upregulated
249 during infection have been postulated to be crucial for fungal virulence and likely act
250 as typical effectors (Saur et al. 2021). In fungi amenable to genetic manipulation, the
251 knock-out of effector genes and subsequent genetic complementation coupled with

252 determination of fungal virulence is the method of choice to subsequently molecularly
253 understand the contribution of individual effectors to fungal virulence.

254 Stable genetic modification of grass powdery mildews can currently not be achieved
255 but because powdery mildews exclusively penetrate the epidermal cells of host leaves,
256 the genetic modification of epidermal cells using biolistic delivery is widely used to
257 study *Blumeria* effector functions and disease development. Initially, transient-induced
258 gene silencing (TIGS) was developed to study the effect of RNAi-mediated silencing
259 of host genes on *Blumeria* infection and fungal penetration rates. Biolistic delivery of
260 RNAi constructs targeting a range of immunity-related wheat proteins, such as a plant
261 chitinase, increased the *Bgt* penetration rate on transgenic cells (Schweizer et al.
262 1999), and RNAi-mediated silencing of the *Mlo* gene in barley, a negative regulator of
263 resistance to *Blumeria* whose expression is necessary for successful infection,
264 significantly increased resistance of transgenic cells to *Bh* infection (Douchkov et al.
265 2005). Based on these studies, Host-induced gene-silencing (HIGS) approaches were
266 developed. Here, targeting of fungal genes with RNAi constructs expressed in the plant
267 host leads to decreased penetration by or microcolony formation of grass powdery
268 mildews. Nowara et al. 2010 targeted 76 *Bh* genes expressed during *Blumeria* infection
269 using biolistic delivery of RNAi constructs into single barley epidermal cells. Silencing
270 of 21% of these genes was found to significantly reduce fungal penetration after
271 challenge infection of the RNAi-expressing barley epidermis cells with *Bh*. As a proof
272 of concept, RNAi-constructs targeting two of these genes encoding for fungal 1-3- β -
273 glucanosyltransferases (GTF1 and GTF2) were additionally introduced to wheat by
274 viral delivery, resulting in a significantly decreased penetration rate by *Bgt*. RNAi-
275 mediated silencing of *GTF1* in stable transgenic barley resulted in reduced *Bh* disease
276 symptoms (% of area covered in fungal mycelium)(Nowara et al. 2010). To test weather

277 effector genes can be targeted by HIGS approaches, EKA_AVRA₁₀ (Ridout et al. 2006)
278 was silenced by biolistic delivery of an RNAi constructs into barley epidermal cells,
279 resulting in reduced virulence of *Bh* (Nowara et al. 2010) and similar result have been
280 obtained for ROPIP1 (Nottensteiner et al. 2018) . HIGS approaches had also been
281 employed for the investigation of *Bgt* genes (Schaefer et al. 2020). As a proof-of-
282 concept experiment, an RNAi construct targeting the *Blumeria* housekeeping gene β 2-
283 *tub* was delivered to wheat epidermal cells and led to a significant reduction of
284 penetration by *Bgt*. Additionally, transgenic wheat lines stably expressing RNAi
285 constructs targeting three *Bgt* effectors were generated, resulting in impaired primary
286 haustorium formation (Schaefer et al. 2020).

287 In an initial broad range screen of *Bh* CSEPs, HIGS biolistic delivery of RNAi constructs
288 to epidermal cells (from here on referred to as ‘transient HIGS’ or ‘transient silencing’
289 if not specified otherwise) of only 16 % of the tested effector candidates resulted in
290 reduced penetration (8 of 50 tested CSEPs; Table 2, Supplementary Table 1, Pliego
291 et al. 2013). Silencing of an additional set of 22 CSEPs suggested that another 8
292 CSEPs (36%) contribute to fungal penetration success (Aguilar et al. 2016), and this
293 set was extended by observing that *csep0254* (*BLGH_00700*) and *csep0081*
294 (*BLGH_03696*) silencing resulted in significant decrease of fungal penetration (but
295 none of the other members of CSEP family 8 or 12 did) (Ahmed et al. 2016). All
296 *Blumeria* effector candidates that were identified to play a role in fungal virulence by
297 HIGS approaches are displayed in Table 2., candidates that did not result in an altered
298 virulence phenotype upon investigation can be accessed in Supplementary Table 1.
299 Clearly HIGS of *csep* gene transcripts has been fundamental for moving the field
300 forward in terms of identifying crucial *Blumeria* virulence effectors, but the biolistic
301 delivery of constructs is time-consuming. To date, it also remains unknown if HIGS of

302 *AVR* genes leads to loss of avirulence and thus, proliferation of the avirulent *Blumeria*
303 isolate on lines carrying matching resistance genes. It also remains unknown if the lack
304 of phenotypes with regard to other CSEPs is due to functional redundancies of
305 effectors, function at differential time points of infection (e.g. post penetration) or other
306 unknown environmental factors. In addition, the transient HIGS approach does not
307 allow to determine sufficient RNA silencing or off-target silencing quality control. These
308 factors may be associated with instances that question in particular negative data
309 resulting from transient HIGS assay approaches. For example, HIGS of *csep0007*
310 (*BLGH_00874*) resulted in enhanced penetration in one instance (Aguilar et al. 2016)
311 but not another (Pliego et al. 2013), whereas HIGS of *csep0264* (*BLGH_07101*,
312 *BEC1011*) resulted in enhanced *Bh* aggressiveness in Pliego et al. 2013, but not when
313 the approach was applied by Aguilar et al. 2016. These differences may be due to
314 different isolates of *Bh* used in the two studies (Aguilar et al. 2016). Indeed, the
315 transcriptome data of 30 different *Bh* isolates (Lu et al. 2016; Saur et al. 2019a)
316 demonstrate the presence of non-synonymous single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)
317 variations in *csep0264* and the existence of multiple copies of the *csep0264* gene (as
318 assessed by heterozygous SNPs in the *csep0264* transcripts), which could influence
319 the efficiency of RNAi. In turn, *csep0007* is highly conserved in and highly expressed
320 by all these *Bh* isolates and the different observations may result from different
321 experimental conditions applied for transient HIGS. In addition, silencing of *AVR_{a1}*
322 (*csep0008*, *BLGH_03023*, *BEC1001*) did not result in reduced penetration rates
323 (Pliego et al. 2013), but later studies suggest involvement of *AVR_{a1}* in fungal virulence
324 as biolistic delivery-assisted *AVR_{a1}* overexpression increased fungal penetration (Li et
325 al. 2024). Overexpression of crucial *csep* genes in host epidermal cells (from here on
326 referred to as 'transient overexpression' if not specified otherwise) should enhance
327 *Blumeria* penetration due to pre-existent virulence factors upon fungal infection. This

328 approach however also relies on biolistic delivery of respective constructs and as such
329 provided an alternative approach for the molecular-genetic studies on CSEPs
330 (Table 2), but not an advancement in terms of time-intensity. The epidermal cell
331 expression approach does not allow determination of effector protein expression and
332 stability inside host cells *via* western blot analysis and assessment of protein stability
333 requires fusion of effectors to fluorescent tags. Large fluorescent tags may however
334 influence activity of small effectors and without western blot analysis, the integrity of
335 ectopically expressed effector proteins, in particular cleavage of tag from effector,
336 cannot be determined. When relying on these assays, fusion protein integrity by
337 western blot analysis upon transient expression of the proteins in protoplasts of the
338 host plants may be used to assess fusion protein integrity, at least in protoplasts of the
339 homologous host plant (Lu et al. 2016; Saur et al. 2019b).

340 Stable transformation of barley (cultivar Golden Promise) and some cultivars of wheat
341 (cultivar Fielder, Bobwhite etc.) is accessible but this is of course extremely time
342 intensive. Yet, the generation of transgenic lines stably expressing effectors or RNAi
343 constructs for assessing changes in *Blumeria* aggressiveness allows qRT-PCR- and
344 immunoblot-based determination of effector mRNA/protein levels and stability of the
345 proteins and could move the field forward by providing more robust readouts than
346 transient assays. Stable effector gene overexpression in the host might also not lead
347 to conclusive results in terms of signal/noise because the intrinsic secretion of the
348 effectors by the fungus upon infection could be sufficient for full fungal virulence.
349 However, stable effector gene overexpression might provide a platform to assess
350 virulence functions of effectors acting at later timepoint of infection (post-penetration).
351 A more time-saving approach may thus be the use of heterologous plant-microbe
352 systems, e.g. the generation of stable transgenic *Arabidopsis thaliana* lines expressing

353 effectors or the use of lines that lack the host targets (i.e. T-DNA / CRISPR-mediated
354 knock-down or knock-out of host targets). Such lines may then be examined for
355 enhanced susceptibility to more or less adapted powdery mildews or entirely unrelated
356 phytopathogens and this approach had already been successfully employed in recent
357 reports to underline putative effector functions (Liao et al. 2023, see section ‘Host
358 interactors of *Blumeria* CSEPs’ below for detail). Notably, this approach of course
359 required conservation of effector functions or targets between cereals and model
360 plants such as *A. thaliana*.

361 Another time-saving approach for powdery mildew effector biology may be the
362 employment of assays that rely on the heterologous transfer of effector proteins or
363 effector genes from accessible microbial systems into cereals (Ökmen et al. 2021;
364 Upadhyaya et al. 2014). For example, the type-3-secretion-system (T3SS)-mediated
365 delivery of *Bh* effectors *via Pseudomonas fluorescence* had been employed recently
366 (Li et al. 2024; Sabelleck et al. 2024). Although the effector protein levels are too low
367 to assess protein expression or actual transfer to the host cells *via* western blot, in
368 terms of time-intensity, the approach appears advantageous to more established
369 techniques. As such, biological relevance of the observed *Blumeria* virulence
370 phenotypes by the employment of additional controls (e.g. those outlined in Fig. 2)
371 could be comparatively easily assessed and would provide information on effector
372 function specificity (see section below for detail).

373 **Host interactors of *Blumeria* CSEPs**

374 A first step towards understanding effector functions is the identification of host proteins
375 that fungal effectors interact with. State-of-the art is the use of effectors as baits in
376 immunoprecipitation approaches followed by LC-MS/MS analysis of the co-isolated
377 proteins. For this, either effector-specific antibodies are required or more commonly,

378 epitope tagged effector gene expression is employed. The expression of epitope-
379 tagged effector genes in effector knock-out lines of genetically amenable fungal
380 species allows to test for the functionality of the epitope-tagged effectors in terms of
381 virulence and pull-down experiments. However, this approach is not feasible for
382 *Blumeria* effectors. As such, so far yeast 2-hybrid (Y2H) screens followed by various
383 one-to-one interaction assays *in planta* have most frequently been employed to identify
384 CSEP interactors (Barsoum et al. 2019) and resulted in the findings summarised below.
385 Notably, here we specifically focus on effector interactors and the assessment of their
386 involvement in powdery mildew virulence and abstain from summarising the putative
387 function of these host targets.

388 The first Y2H screen involved CSEP0055 (*BLGH_05198*) and resulted in the
389 identification of multiple pathogen-related (PR) proteins (PR1a, PR1b, PR17b and
390 PR17c) as putative targets of CSEP0055. CSEP0443 (BghEfc1, *BLGH_04782*) served
391 as a negative control in these assays. Transient HIGS of PR17c increased *Bh*
392 penetration and whereas its transient overexpression by particle bombardment
393 markedly decreased the *Bh* penetration rate (Zhang et al. 2012). This study set a
394 roadmap for further investigation of *Blumeria* effectors.

395 In 2015, Y2H screens involving CSEP0105 (*BLGH_06498*) and CSEP0162
396 (*BLGH_01256*) found these to associate with the two-small heat-shock proteins
397 sHSP16.9 and sHSP17.5. Transient TIGS of both putative target proteins in barley
398 epidermal cells did not result in an altered *Bh* susceptibility. Yet, in *Escherichia coli*
399 protein extract, sHSP16.9 was shown to prevent heat induced protein aggregation, an
400 effect that decreased when CSEP0105 was added (Ahmed et al. 2015).

401 More recently, an independent Y2H screen identified MONENSIN SENSITIVITY 1
402 (MON1) as interactor of CSEP0162 but not CSEP0105. Notably, CSEP0162 appears

403 to suppress artificially-induced formation of *Bh* haustoria encasements and similar
404 results were seen upon delivery of RNAi constructs targeting HvMON1 *via* biolistic
405 delivery to barley and in *A. thaliana* ecotype NO-0 *mon1* lines (Liao et al. 2023).

406 An additional Y2H screen found CSEP0027 (*BLGH_03653*) to interact with the barley
407 catalase HvCAT1 but not with HvCAT2 and barley stripe mosaic virus (BSMV)- and
408 TIGS-based transient silencing of HvCAT1, but not of HvCAT2, resulted in increased
409 *Bh* penetration (Yuan et al. 2021).

410 *Bgt* AvrPm2 (*BgtE-5845*) recognised by the wheat Pm2 NLR was found by Y2H to
411 interact with the wheat transcription factor TaZF. Association was also detected with
412 the homeologs TaZF_5B, TaZF_5D but not TaZF_4D. However, virus-induced gene-
413 silencing (VIGS) of TaZF did not obviously alter infection rates of *Bgt* on wheat lines
414 lacking Pm2 (Manser et al. 2024).

415 AVR_{A1} (CSEP0008, *BLGH_03023*) and CSEP0491 (BEC1016, *BLGH_07006*) were
416 found to interact with the ER J-domain chaperone HvERdj3B. Transient
417 overexpression of AVR_{A1} and BEC1016 or of HvERdj3B RNAi constructs to epidermal
418 cells increased the *Bh* haustorium formation rate (Li et al. 2024).

419 Most recently, a Y2H screen isolated VSP18 as interactor of CSEP0214
420 (*BLGH_02334*, BEC2) and demonstrated that the VPS18 RING domain being
421 sufficient for interaction (Sabelleck et al. 2024). Combinations of VPS18 and 10
422 randomly selected CSEPs as well as CSEP0214 and two barley proteins with RING
423 domains were employed for determining specificity of the interaction. Transient
424 overexpression of CSEP0214 in epidermal cells did not result in enhanced *Bh*
425 penetration but reduced callose deposition in papillae and artificially-induced
426 haustorium encasement. Notably, bacterial T3SS-mediated delivery of CSEP0214 to

427 incompatible (*Mla1/Mla3*-triggered immunity) barley leaf tissue increased fungal
428 growth (Sabelleck et al. 2024).

429 The only non-yeast-based interactor screen of *Blumeria* CSEPs focused on
430 CSEP0064 (BEC1054, BLGH_06959). For this, recombinant His-tagged CSEP0064
431 was incubated with barley protein extracts and thereafter purified using Ni-columns.
432 BEC1005 (BLGH_03125) was used as a control and this led to the LC-MS/MS-based
433 identification of Elongation Factor 1 gamma (eEF1 γ), a Glutathione-S-Transferase
434 (GST), a Malate Dehydrogenase (MDH), PR5 and PR10 as CSEP0064 interactors.
435 Further experiments involving these interactors had not yet been performed
436 (Pennington et al. 2016).

437 **Structure versus function**

438 A significant step forward in the functional investigation of proteins has been the
439 predictions of protein structures and more recently the availability of the user-friendly
440 AlphaFold prediction platform (Abramson et al. 2024; Mirdita et al. 2022).
441 Computational predictions (Bauer et al. 2021; Pedersen et al. 2012; Seong and
442 Krasileva 2023; Spanu et al. 2010) and experimentally solved structures (Cao et al.
443 2023; Pennington et al. 2019) have demonstrated that a significant proportion of
444 CSEPs adopt a common structural fold reminiscent of fungal ribonucleases (RNases)
445 and are therefore also known as RALPHs (for RNase-Like Proteins associated with
446 Hauستoria) (Spanu 2017). Notably, RALPHs have been described in detail previously
447 (Cao et al. 2023; Kusch et al. 2024b; Pedersen et al. 2012; Spanu 2017) and we
448 therefore only make a note about the role of this structural fold with respect to virulence
449 function based on recent structure-function analyses: The residues constituting the
450 active sites in fungal RNases are not conserved in the RALPH proteins but, at least *in*
451 *vitro*, the recombinant RALPH-member CSEP0064 (BEC1054, BLGH_06959)

452 interacted with total barley RNA and 28S rRNA (Pennington et al. 2019). However,
453 none of the by Cao et al. 2023 investigated RALPH CSEPs showed enzymatic
454 activities typical of fungal RNases as catalytical ribonuclease activity or RNA binding
455 affinity (Cao et al. 2023). This and the diverse host interactors identified for multiple
456 different RALPH CSEPs leads to the conclusion that RALPH CSEP virulence functions
457 likely result from neofunctionalization and can be separated from the core (RNase-like)
458 structure. The same has been observed for other fungal effector protein families
459 (Outram et al. 2022).

460 **Conclusions, constrains and putative future research directions**

461 Despite the technical constrains associated with molecular and genetic research on
462 obligate biotrophic pathogens, extensive functional studies on *Blumeria* CSEPs and
463 other virulence proteins were performed. This underlines that powdery mildews serve
464 as excellent models for studying biotrophic pathogens of cereal hosts, including cell
465 biological approaches (Hückelhoven and Panstruga 2011). Additionally, they provide
466 insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying obligate biotrophy in agriculturally
467 important cereal pathogens.

468 Significant advancements have enhanced our understanding of the effector repertoire
469 of grass powdery mildews. Extensive bioinformatic analysis has facilitated the
470 identification of a vast array of effector candidates. Progress has been made in
471 understanding the origin and the evolution of the massively proliferated *Blumeria*
472 effector repertoire and insights into structure and structural similarities among various
473 effector candidates were obtained. The identification of AVR effectors amongst the
474 predicted *Blumeria* candidate effectors and proteomic approaches of infected
475 epidermal tissue had provided experimental evidence for predicted candidate effector
476 genes to encode functional fungal effector proteins. Several host targets of *Blumeria*

477 candidate effectors were identified in unbiased Y2H approaches and interactions
478 confirmed by targeted *in planta* interaction studies. With the continuous increase in
479 knowledge including from other host-microbe systems, the field moves forward and
480 continuously employs additional controls to strengthen the observations with regard to
481 host interactors serving as true virulence targets for fungal effectors. Controls mostly
482 involved the employment of other effectors in host target screens (Fig. 2A) or
483 confirmation of the identified interaction by independent approaches. Recent reports
484 also applied more specificity controls to underline the distinctiveness of the interactions
485 between effector and host target and phenotypes identified (Liao et al. 2023; Manser
486 et al. 2024; Sabelleck et al. 2024). Such controls can range from the identification and
487 employment of specific host interactor protein domains, related host proteins, that may
488 not interact with the effector of interest to the generation and use of chimeric effector
489 constructs (Fig. 2B). The latter was proven to be in particular effective in pinpointing
490 effector regions and residues required for the activation of host NLRs by AVR effectors
491 (Bauer et al. 2021; Cao et al. 2023; Manser et al. 2024). Manser et al. 2024 applied
492 the use of host target related proteins as an additional specificity control (Fig. 2B),
493 which highlighted the specificity of the interaction between AvrPm2 and TaZF.
494 Additionally, assisted by the use of AlphaFold predictions, chimeric host targets or
495 mutations of effector residues may be generated (Fig. 2B). In practice, it will likely not
496 be possible to employ all these options, but the use of additional controls for the
497 specificity of protein-protein interactions will provide additional credibility to molecular
498 biology research on powdery mildews. In the future, structures of effectors and host
499 targets may in certain cases be obtained, but to date this is not a widely-applicable
500 task in this field of research.

501 For many host interactor proteins of *Blumeria* candidate effectors, RNAi-based knock
502 down of the interactor transcripts led to increased host immunity towards powdery

503 mildew and/or overexpression to decreased host immunity suggesting negative
504 regulation of the host targets' intrinsic function by the CSEP of interest. Our inability of
505 genetically prove the importance of host targets as true virulence targets of powdery
506 mildew CSEPs is a major drawback for understanding the molecular manipulations of
507 host factors by powdery mildews. To date we rely on (i) pathogenicity phenotypes upon
508 silencing and overexpression of effectors and (ii) pathogenicity phenotypes upon
509 silencing and overexpression of host targets. Ideally, we would be able to demonstrate
510 that the manipulations of the host targets by the effectors of interest is the cause for
511 the differential virulence phenotypes (Fig. 3). The constrains in this regard are due to
512 the fact that (i) phenotypes upon transient expression of effectors or effector silencing
513 constructs are highly time-intensive and (ii) stable knock-out of host targets to
514 determine loss of virulence phenotypes mediated by effector silencing or
515 overexpression is not easily possible in barley and wheat. Even if these factors were
516 improved by technical advancements, we would likely nevertheless face the common
517 challenges in effector biology. These include redundancy between effector functions,
518 lethality upon knock-out of certain host targets and the possibility of multiple host
519 targets being responsible for the effectors capacity to change fungal virulence
520 phenotypes.

521 In the future we may be able to assess the role of effectors in the establishment of a
522 biotrophic lifestyle by combining CRISPR of host targets or employing BSMV-mediated
523 silencing of host targets followed by transient expression of effectors or effector RNAi
524 constructs or potentially transferring effectors *via* the use of synthetic biology such as
525 other microbial delivery systems.

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529 **Funding**

530 IMLS and MBS are funded by the DFG Emmy Noether Programme (SA 4093/1-1 to
531 IMLS) from the DFG (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft / German Research
532 Foundation). IMLS also acknowledges support from the Cluster of Excellence on Plant
533 Sciences (CEPLAS) funded by the DFG under Germany's Excellence Strategy – EXC
534 2048/1 – Project ID: 390686111 and funding from the DFG Collaborative Research
535 Centre Project-ID 414786233 (SFB 1403). Research of MCM is supported by the DFG.

536

537 **Acknowledgements**

538 We may not have included all reports on *Blumeria* effectors here and sincerely
539 apologize to all authors whose work we have not included. We would like to thank
540 Pietro Spanu and Lamprinos Frantzeskakis for providing insights into the prediction of
541 *Bh* effector genes as well as Ralph Panstruga and Björn Sabelleck for clarification of
542 the most recent *Bh* effector prediction pipeline.

543

544 **Conflict of interest**

545 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

546

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Figure legends

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of *Blumeria spp.* infection on the leaf surface of a compatible cereal cultivar. Upon contact with the leaf surface, the conidiospore forms a short primary germ tube (after ~1 hour) followed by the formation of a secondary germ tube that leads to the formation of the appressorium and later the penetration peg (after ~16 h post infection). The penetration peg breaches the plant cell wall but not the plant plasma membrane and eventually leads to the formation of a functional haustorium feeding structure in the periplasm (~24 h post infection). The haustorium serves as the primary site for the exchange of effectors and nutrients between host and fungal cells. This allows the fungus to produce epiphytic mycelium, secondary haustoria (after ~ 3 days after the start of infection) and the formation of new conidiospores (after ~ 5 days).

Figure 2. Putative controls for the identification of specific effector-host target interactions. **A)** identification of putative effector host targets by screening for protein interactors. Often, unrelated effectors of the same organism are used as a negative control. **B)** Confirmation of specificity of the in A) identified interactions by the employment of additional specificity controls. Interaction screens of mutated and chimeric effectors (chimera between interacting and non-interacting effector) with the host interactor may be used as a control for effector interaction specificity. Additionally, interaction studies between proteins related to the host interactor as well as chimeric host interactors (chimera between host interactor a non-interacting related host protein) and the effector of interest may be employed as controls for the interaction specificity of the putative host target.

Figure 3. Connecting effectors and host interactors to pathogen virulence phenotypes

A) Identification of putative host targets is based on the identification of host interactors by established protein-protein interaction screens. **B)** The physiological relevance of effectors for fungal virulence is commonly stated by the identification of differential virulence phenotypes upon silencing or overexpression of an effector of interest in a compatible pathogen-host interaction or in heterologous systems. **C)** Connecting protein-protein interaction with differential virulence phenotype displayed in the presence of the effector of interest.

Figure 1

Figure 2

A Identification of effector interactors

B Specificity controls for effector-host target interactions

Figure 3

Table 1 - Overview of long-read *Blumeria* genome assemblies

Species	NCBI Taxonomy ID species/ formae specialis	isolate	NCBI Taxonomy ID isolate	GenBank ID	Project ID / Database	Platform	Reference
<i>Blumeria hordei</i>	2867405	DH14 ^a	546991	GCA_900239735	OENG01 (WGS ^c)	Pacific Biosciences	Frantzeskakis et al. 2018
<i>Blumeria hordei</i>	2867405	RACE1	n/a ^b	GCA_900237765	UNSH01 (WGS ^c)	Pacific Biosciences	Frantzeskakis et al. 2018
<i>Blumeria hordei</i>	2867405	K1	1283759	GCA_900638725	CAAAHF01 (WGS ^c)	Oxford nanopore	Saur et al. 2019a
<i>Blumeria hordei</i>	2867405	SK1	1283759 variant	GCA_023065745	JAJOCF01 (WGS ^c)	Oxford nanopore	Kusch et al. 2024
<i>Blumeria graminis</i> forma specialis <i>tritici</i>	62690	CHE_96224 ^a	1268274	GCA_900519115	517853 (nucleotide collection)	Pacific Biosciences	Müller et al. 2019
<i>Blumeria graminis</i> forma specialis <i>tritici</i>	62690	ISR_7	n/a ^b	GCA_927323605	CAKMHR02 (WGS ^c)	Pacific Biosciences	Müller et al. 2022
<i>Blumeria graminis</i> forma specialis <i>tritici</i>	62690	CHVD_04220 1	n/a	n/a	n/a	Pacific Biosciences	Kunz et al. 2024a
<i>Blumeria graminis</i> forma specialis <i>tritici</i>	62690	Wtn1	n/a ^b	GCA_024363405	JALMLO01 (WGS ^c)	combination Illumina/Oxford nanopore	Nallathambi et al. 2024
<i>Blumeria graminis</i> forma specialis <i>tritiale</i>	1689686	THUN-12	n/a ^b	GCA_905067625	CAJHIT01 (WGS ^c)	Pacific Biosciences RSII	Müller et al. 2021

^areference isolate, ^bnot available, ^cWhole genome shotgun

Table 2 – *Blumeria* effector candidates that resulted in virulence phenotypes (compatible interactions only) upon overexpression (OX) / host-induced gene-silencing (HIGS) in the host (epidermal) cells.

Effector name or CSEP ^a /BEC ^b identifier	Gene ID	Pathogen isolate	Host organism	Method	Virulence phenotype	Expression vector (promotor)	References
CSEP0004/ BEC5	BLGH_04235	<i>Bh</i> K1	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient OX ^c	Increased fungal penetration ^e	pUbi-GWY (pZmUbi)	Schmidt et al. 2014
CSEP0007	BLGH_00874	<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPKTA30N (p35S)	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0008/ AVR _{A1}	BLGH_03023	<i>Bh</i> C15	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient OX ^c	Increased fungal penetration ^e	pUbi-GW-Nos (pZmUbi)	Li et al. 2024
CSEP0025	BLGH_02741	<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPKTA30N (p35S)	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0027	BLGH_03653	<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPK(b?)007 (p35S/pZmUbi?) ^h	Yuan et al. 2021
		<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	unknown	Yuan et al. 2021
CSEP0055	BLGH_05198	<i>Bh</i> DH14	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPKTA30N (p35S)	Zhang et al. 2012

		<i>Bh</i> CH4.8	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pTA30 (p35S)	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0064/ BEC1054	BLGH_06959	<i>Bgt</i> Fielder	<i>T. aestivum</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Increased microcolony formation	pActR1R2-SCV (pActin)	Pennington et al. 2019
		<i>Peronospora tabacina</i>	<i>N. benthamiana</i>	Transient OX ^c	Increased sporangium formation rate	pK7FWG2 (p35S)	Pennington et al. 2019
CSEP0081	BLGH_03696	<i>Bh</i> DH14	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPKTA30N (p35S)	Ahmed et al. 2016
CSEP0105	BLGH_06498	<i>Bh</i> DH14	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPKTA30N (p35S)	Ahmed et al. 2015
CSEP0128	BLGH_04692	<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPKTA30N (p35S)	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0135/ BEC1018	BLGH_03164	<i>Bh</i> CH4.8	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pTA30 (p35S)	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0139	BLGH_07004	<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPK(b?)007 (p35S/pZmUbi?) ^h	Li et al. 2021
		<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient OX ^c	Increased fungal penetration ^e	pUbi-GW (pZmUbi)	Li et al. 2021
CSEP0162	BLGH_01256	<i>Bh</i> DH14	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPKTA30N (p35S)	Ahmed et al. 2015

CSEP0182	BLGH_06939	<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPK(b?)007 (p35S/pZmUbi?) ^h	Li et al. 2021
		<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient OX ^c	Increased fungal penetration ^e	pUbi-GW (pZmUbi)	Li et al. 2021
CSEP0191/ BEC1038	BLGH_02169	<i>Bh</i> CH4.8	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pTA30 (p35S)	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0196/ BEC1040	BLGH_06893	<i>Bh</i> CH4.8	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pTA30 (p35S)	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0211	BLGH_00733	<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPKTA30N (p35S)	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0214 (<i>G. orontii</i> homolog, GoBEC2)	BLGH_02334	<i>Erysiphe pisi</i> Birmingham	<i>A. thaliana</i>	Stable OX ^d	Increased fungal penetration ^e	pPAM-PAT-GWY (p35S)	Schmidt et al. 2014
CSEP0247	BLGH_02307	<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPKTA30N (p35S)	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0254	BLGH_00700	<i>Bh</i> DH14	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPKTA30N (p35S)	Ahmed et al. 2016
CSEP0264/ BEC1011	BLGH_07101	<i>Bh</i> CH4.8	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pTA30 (p35S)	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0345	BLGH_04632	<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPKTA30N (p35S)	Aguilar et al. 2016

CSEP0420	BLGH_01483	<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPKTA30N (p35S)	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0422	BLGH_00600	<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPKTA30N (p35S)	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0491/ BEC1016	BLGH_07006	<i>Bh</i> CH4.8	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pTA30 (p35S)	Pliego et al. 2013
		<i>Bh</i> C15	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient OX ^c	Increased fungal penetration ^e	pUbi-GW-Nos (pZmUbi)	Li et al. 2024
BEC3	-	<i>Bh</i> K1	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient OX ^c	Increased fungal penetration ^e	pUbi-GWY (pZmUbi)	Schmidt et al. 2014
BEC1005	BLGH_03125	<i>Bh</i> CH4.8	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pTA30 (p35S)	Pliego et al. 2013
		<i>Bh</i> CH4.8	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pTA30 (p35S)	Pliego et al. 2013
BEC1019	BLGH_04871	<i>Bgt</i>	<i>T. aestivum</i>	Stable HIGS ^d	Decreased microcolony formation/ fungal biomass	pCAMBIA2301 (p35S)	Zhang et al. 2019
		<i>Bgt</i>	<i>T. aestivum</i>	Stable OX ^d	Increased microcolony	CTAPi-GW-3HA (p35S)	Zhang et al. 2019

					formation/ fungal biomass		
					Decreased microcolony formation/ fungal biomass	pCAMBIA2301-GW (p35S)	Zhang et al. 2019
		<i>G. graminis</i> var. <i>tritici</i> LY3-21	<i>T. aestivum</i>	Stable HIGS ^d			
					Increased microcolony formation/ fungal biomass	CTAPi-GW-3HA (p35S)	Zhang et al. 2019
		<i>G. graminis</i> var. <i>tritici</i> LY3-21	<i>T. aestivum</i>	Stable OX ^d			
EKA-AVR _{A10}	-	<i>Bh</i> K1	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Increased fungal penetration ^e	pUbi-GWY (pZmUbi)	Schmidt et al. 2014
					Decreased fungal penetration ^e	pIPKTA30N (p35S)	Nottensteiner et al. 2018
ROPIP1	-	<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient HIGS ^c			
					Increased fungal penetration ^e	pGY1	Nottensteiner et al. 2018
		<i>Bh</i> A6	<i>H. vulgare</i>	Transient OX ^c			
SvrPm3 ^{a1/f 1}	-	<i>Bgt</i> JIW2	<i>T. aestivum</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^g	pIPKb007 (pZmUbi)	Schaefer et al. 2020
					Decreased fungal penetration ^g	pIPKb007 (pZmUbi)	Schaefer et al. 2020
Bgt_Bcg-6	-	<i>Bgt</i> JIW2	<i>T. aestivum</i>	Transient HIGS ^c			
					Decreased fungal penetration ^g	pIPKb007 (pZmUbi)	Schaefer et al. 2020
		<i>Bgt</i> JIW2	<i>T. aestivum</i>	Transient HIGS ^c			
Bgt_Bcg-7	-	<i>Bgt</i> JIW2	<i>T. aestivum</i>	Transient HIGS ^c	Decreased fungal penetration ^g	pIPKb007 (pZmUbi)	Schaefer et al. 2020

^aCSEP = Candidate secreted effector proteins ^bBEC = *B*lumeria *h*ordei effector candidate ^cmediated by biolistic delivery of constructs to epidermal cells ^dHIGS or overexpression in stable plant lines ^eFungal penetration quantified by assessment of the haustorial index (= rate of appressorium-forming spores that form a haustorium) ^fFungal penetration quantified by assessment of rate of appressorium-forming spores that form a primary haustorium.

Supplementary Table 1 - *Blumeria* effector candidates that were tested for changes to *Blumeria* virulence upon transient overexpression or host-induced gene-silencing (HIGS) via biolistic delivery to host epidermal cells.

Effector name or CSEP^a /BEC^b identifier	Gene ID	Methods	Reference
CSEP0001/BEC1007	BLGH_07017	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0002/BEC1004	BLGH_06552	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0004/BEC1003	BLGH_04235	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0005/BEC1002	BLGH_05489	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0007/BEC1009	BLGH_00874	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0008/BEC1001	BLGH_03023	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0017/BEC1043	BLGH_01448	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0037/BEC1023	BLGH_01403	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0052/BEC1	BLGH_04851	Transient OX ^c	Schmidt et al. 2014
CSEP0061/BEC1048	BLGH_03215	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0062	BLGH_06688	Transient HIGS ^c	Ahmed et al. 2016
CSEP0069/BEC1055	BLGH_05478	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0072/BEC1050	BLGH_05465	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0073/BEC1059	BLGH_06880	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0080/BEC1014	BLGH_05017	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0082/BEC1012	BLGH_05005	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0090/BEC1008	BLGH_03700	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0095/BEC1041	BLGH_06670	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0096/BEC1017	BLGH_05228	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0097/BEC1061	BLGH_05016	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0102/BEC1021	BLGH_07019	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0104/BEC1027	BLGH_06935	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0110/BEC1062	BLGH_03168	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0130/BEC1063	BLGH_04698	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013

CSEP0139	BLGH_07004	Transient HIGS ^c	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0142/BEC1022	BLGH_00893	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0145	BLGH_07001	Transient HIGS ^c	Ahmed et al. 2016
CSEP0152/BEC1065	BLGH_07030	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0156	BLGH_05718	Transient HIGS ^c	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0192/BEC1020	BLGH_04344	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0196/BEC1037	BLGH_06893	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0202	BLGH_01268	Transient HIGS ^c	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0210/BEC1035	BLGH_02927	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0214/BEC2	BLGH_02334	Transient OX ^c	Schmidt et al. 2014 Sabelleck et al. 2024
CSEP0216	BLGH_00921	Transient HIGS ^c	Ahmed et al. 2016
CSEP0222	BLGH_01062	Transient HIGS ^c	Ahmed et al. 2016
CSEP0225	BLGH_05276	Transient HIGS ^c	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0228/BEC1033	BLGH_06425	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0231/BEC1024	BLGH_05436	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0232/BEC1047	BLGH_02416	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
CSEP0235	BLGH_03631	Transient HIGS ^c	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0244	BLGH_06152	Transient HIGS ^c	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0264	BLGH_07101	Transient HIGS ^c	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0307	BLGH_03939	Transient HIGS ^c	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0313	BLGH_02704	Transient HIGS ^c	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0323	BLGH_02939	Transient HIGS ^c	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0324	BLGH_00732	Transient HIGS ^c	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0325	BLGH_00837	Transient HIGS ^c	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0337	BLGH_06050	Transient HIGS ^c	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0385	BLGH_04126	Transient HIGS ^c	Aguilar et al. 2016
CSEP0398	BLGH_04353	Transient HIGS ^c	Ahmed et al. 2016
BEC1047	BLGH_01709	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013

BEC4	-	Transient OX ^c	Schmidt et al. 2014
BEC1066	BLGH_03146	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
BEC1010	BLGH_03366	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
BEC1013	BLGH_00436	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
BEC1025	BLGH_03118	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
BEC1029	BLGH_06461	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
BEC1031	BLGH_03180	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
BEC1032	BLGH_03653	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
BEC1034	-	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
BEC1036	BLGH_03139	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
BEC1066	BLGH_04340	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013
BEC1067	BLGH_04829	Transient HIGS ^c	Pliego et al. 2013

^aCSEP = Candidate secreted effector proteins ^bBEC = Blumeria hordei effector candidate ^cmediated by biolistic delivery of constructs to epidermal cells